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Master's Final Project

**Impact of SARS-CoV-2 on the Coronavirus
Literature through Dynamic Topics**

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to study the impact of SARS-CoV-2 in the coronavirus literature. We want to analyze how this virus has erupted in a collection of coronavirus articles (CORD-19). We want to know how, if at all, it has changed the direction of the research line.

This collection contains articles of all types of coronaviruses. We want to find how coronavirus research has evolved during the three most relevant coronavirus events: SARS-CoV-1, MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV-2 viruses. This task is in the domain of natural language processing, and dynamic topic models will be used to solve it.

We will use three models to solve it, and their performance will be compared. The models we will use are: Dynamic Topic Model, BERTopic and Dynamic Embedded Topic Model. The dynamic topic models will be used to generate the evolution of the different topics of the corpus. By means of this, it is possible to observe which words are related within the topic to determine their relationship with each other. In addition, it is also possible to see the appearances or disappearances of words.

The topics containing drugs or treatments will be analyzed to study the relationships between the words that generate the different models. The objective is to see if the topic in which the drugs are found is directly related to the disease or symptoms in the same topic.

Availability and Implementation

The implementation of this project is available at [github](https://github.com/drugs4covid/dynamic-topics-cord19)¹. The processed data, the resources used and the trained models are available at [zenodo](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129601)².

¹<https://github.com/drugs4covid/dynamic-topics-cord19>

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129601>

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The health crisis caused by SARS-CoV-2 has marked a milestone in human history. The management of this crisis brings with it a multitude of challenges and difficulties. One of these is the management of information. A large volume of information has been generated due to the amount of research that has been carried out and is ongoing.

An investigation is carried out in a specific period, and to a large extent, as an evolution of topics discussed in previous investigations. Also, it may deal with one or several topics. Similarly, the themes, conditioned by the research that deals with them evolve. Identifying the topic(s) addressed in research is difficult and requires an understanding of the context of the problem. All this makes finding information on a particular topic a very complicated task.

This work aims to analyze a large and growing collection of documents to find the underlying topics in the texts, their evolution over time, and to identify texts that deal with similar topics. In particular, we have carried out the analysis on the COVID-19 corpus, which contains scientific articles on SARS-COV-2 and coronaviruses.

There are a multitude of difficulties with this task, but the main one is that there is a large volume of data and that it is in an unstructured format, which makes it difficult to identify the underlying themes and their progression over time. Because of this, it is clear that this task is very difficult to complete manually by human experts. To complete it, it is necessary to apply natural language processing techniques. One of the methods that allow us to identify the existing topics in the corpus and their evolution over time is dynamic topic modeling.

With the dynamic topic models, we want to study the impact of SARS-CoV-2 in the coronavirus literature. We want to identify which diseases, symptoms or causes are related to SARS-COV-2 and its associated drugs. There have been viruses that preceded SARS-COV-2 that also belonged to the coronavirus family. Therefore, we also want to analyze how the coronavirus topic evolves and what incidents and events it responds to.

Chapter 2

Word Representations

One of the first ways to represent the words of a text in a computable form is through vector space models (VSMs). VSMs are algebraic models that represent the words of a text as vectors. These were introduced by Salton et al. [1975] for the “the experimental automatic SMART document retrieval system” of Ide and Salton [1971]. Their approach consisted in representing each document as a point in space (vector in a vector space), so that semantic correlations depend on the distance between documents. In this way, if a document is next to another is because they are semantically similar, but if it is far away its because they are semantically very different. This vector space is known as semantic space.

For building the semantic space and for processing the texts, word-context, term-document or pair-pattern matrices can be generated (Turney and Pantel [2010]). In the context of this project, the most relevant ones are the term-document and the word-context matrices.

In the word-context matrix (also called term-term and word-word co-occurrence matrix), the dimensions are composed of the vocabulary of the corpus concerning itself. In this way, each word in the corpus vocabulary is shown as a vector of the frequency to which it appears next to the rest of the words. This word or term frequency is referred to as TF (which is explained in more detail in section 2.3.1).

This matrix is used to support the distributional hypothesis. This hypothesis assumes that words that occur in related contexts often have similar meanings (Harris [1954]; Deerwester et al. [1990]), therefore, words with similar vectors will have a similar meaning.

In the term-document matrix, the dimensions are composed of the documents and the vocabulary of the corpus. In this way, each document is shown as a vector of the frequency of the terms of the corpus vocabulary appearing in it.

This matrix is used to support the bag-of-words (BOW) hypothesis. This hypothesis accepts that the documents are just a bag of words, assuming that the order of the words is irrelevant and that they are conditionally independent of each other (Salton et al. [1975]).

Although to calculate the term-document matrix the TF metric is also used, the main problem is that the term frequency is not the best metric for investigating relations between terms and measuring how significant a term is to a document in a corpus.

This is because TF assigns more importance to words that are repeated more often. However, words that are repeated a lot in all documents do not contribute much, such as "the". That is why some other metrics appear for weighting each word such as Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF), which is explained in more detail in section 2.3.2. TF-IDF is considered a more accurate metric because adds an inverse document frequency factor to reduce the relevance of words that appear in more documents.

2.1 Word Embeddings

The main problem of this type of VSMs is that the documents are represented by sparse long vectors. The dimensionality of these vectors depends on the vocabulary of the corpus to which they belong, which implies that the more documents in the corpus, the more probable it will be that the vectors will be more sparse. This sparsity requires large memory usage and big-time complexity.

The alternative to this are the embeddings. These are short dense vectors of considerably reduced dimensionality. The most common embeddings dimensionality is 300 (Yin and Shen [2018]), which is much lower than the vocabulary of a corpus. Due to dimensionality reduction, word similarity calculations are carried out more efficiently (Gutiérrez and Keith [2019]).

The following models are *static embeddings*. The static embedding models learn only one embedding for each word in the corpus vocabulary. This restriction introduces several problems in the semantic representation of the word. It generates a single vector for each word, assuming that they have a unique semantic meaning. It omits that the word may appear in different contexts, which is a problem with polysemous words.

2.1.1 Word2vec

There are several methods for computing embeddings, Mikolov et al. [2013a] proposed the Continuous Bag-of-Words Model (CBOW) and Continuous Skip-gram Model architectures, both implemented in the word2vec software tool (usually the two architectures are referred to by word2vec).

These architectures are inverse, but both approaches use shallow neural networks to learn word embeddings. On the one hand, CBOW predicts the word corresponding to a context of neighbouring words, both preceding and following the word to be found. On the other hand, Skip-gram predicts the context of neighbouring words for a particular word. The main strength of word2vec is that, compared to state-of-the-art methods of its time, similar performance is achieved at lower computational cost.

Mikolov et al. [2013b] introduced various improvements to the word2vec algorithms in terms of vector quality and training speed. These improvements are: Hierarchical Softmax, Negative Sampling and Subsampling of Frequent Words.

- The Hierarchical Softmax (HS) increases computational efficiency by reducing the evaluation of the W output nodes to $\log_2(W)$, so that the process of obtaining the probability distribution is accelerated.

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- The Negative Sampling addresses the problem of updating weights. While training a neural network weight updates are performed at each epoch, which in combination with the vocabulary size of a corpus creates a problem when updating all the weights. With this improvement, only a small set of “negative” words are chosen to update their weights. Negative words are those that should not be related to the current input of the neural network.
- The Subsampling of Frequent Words is used to remove frequent words from the training phase. The more frequent a word occurs in the text more likely it is to be deleted. This is because in the texts, words like articles, appear many times, more than needed to learn a good vector for them. Moreover, the times they occur also do not yield much information about the words that go with them.

2.1.2 GloVe

Another relevant static embedding is Global Vectors (GloVe), proposed by Pennington et al. [2014]. GloVe infers word relationships from statistics. It uses global word information from the word co-occurrence matrix to extract semantic relationships. This method constructs the co-occurrence matrix and then applies matrix factorization to reduce the dimensionality. Dimensionality reduction is carried out by minimising the “reconstruction loss”. This loss attempts to identify the lowest dimensional representations that explain most of the variance in the high dimensional data.

2.1.3 FastText

Word2vec has two main problems. On the one hand, is unable to handle words outside the learned vocabulary. On the other hand, it does not take into account the correlation between words with the same stems. The word embeddings are learned based exclusively on the context in which they appear, ignoring the morphology of the words.

To address these issues, based on the word2vec skip-gram model, Mikolov et al. [2017] presented FastText. In this method, each word is divided using n-grams to generate sub-words. The problem with this method is that the vocabulary grows considerably. Therefore, to generate the vector of a word, you have to aggregate all the vectors of the sub-words that form it. This causes a rise in computational complexity and memory demand. Due to the large number of additional vectors generated by the subwords, the authors decided to use hashing to store them in memory to reduce the dimensionality (Weinberger et al. [2009]).

In this approach, the smallest units for training become sub-words, whereas in the previous approaches they were words. The goal is to exploit the rich information in the internal structure of words.

2.2 Contextual Embeddings

One of the main problems with conventional word embeddings is the inability to deal with the polysemy. There are several ways to deal with this problem and evaluate the multiple contexts in which a word can appear.

2.2.1 Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers

One way to deal with the problem of polysemy is at the word level, assuming each word has one or more meanings depending on the context. Devlin et al. [2018] introduced Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT). BERT is a language representation model based on transformers.

The Transformer architecture was introduced by Vaswani et al. [2017]. This architecture is a neural network focused on the attention mechanism that avoids recurrent neural networks. The Transformer architecture is an iterative process consisting of multiple sequentially connected Encoder-Decoder sets. At each Transformer step, the Encoder transforms the input into a representation in a dimensional space. Meanwhile, the Decoder processes the output of the Encoder and passes it to the next Encoder-Decoder set. From the first Transformer iteration, the Decoder will process both the Encoder output and the output of the previous Transformer cycle before passing it to the next Encoder-Decoder cycle. However BERT, as its name indicates, is a technique focused only on generating language representations, so it only has the Encoder module.

2.2.2 BERT improvements

The BERT architecture has been improved several times to create different models. However, one of the first was that of Liu et al. [2019]. They noticed that the BERT network suffered from undertraining problems. Therefore, the authors presented several modifications to the BERT pre-training process. With these improvements the model improves significantly, achieving results comparable to other state-of-the-art models. This improved model was named the Robustly optimized BERT approach (RoBERTa). However, both the BERT and RoBERTa models have been outperformed by several architectures. One of these is the one presented by He et al. [2020]. These authors were able to improve the BERT and RoBERTa models by modifying the way the words were represented and by adding absolute positions in the decoding layer. They call this architecture the DECODING-ENHANCED BERT WITH DISENTANGLED ATTENTION (DEBERTA).

2.2.3 Sentence-BERT

Another way to tackle this problem is at the sentence level, representing the entire sentence in the semantic space. For this purpose, Reimers and Gurevych [2019] developed Sentence-BERT (SBERT). SBERT is a modification of the pre-trained BERT network to obtain embeddings of semantically similar sentences. SBERT was developed because BERT had severe computational overhead when working with complete sentences, which made it impossible to tackle the task in a reasonable amount of time. This modification of BERT includes siamese and triplet networks capable of constructing a semantic space of sentences where similar sentences are close.

2.3 Techniques

2.3.1 Term Frequency

One of the most famous word metrics used for measuring the word distribution is the TF (term frequency). The TF proposed by Luhn [1958] assumes that the frequency with which a term appears in an article is a helpful indicator of its importance. The words (terms) in a text, are taken one at a time (unigrams), and their frequency is used to generate the matrix representation of the document.

2.3.2 Term Frequency – Inverse Document Frequency

According to Aizawa [2003] TF-IDF (term frequency – inverse document frequency) “is one of the most commonly used term weighting schemes in today’s information retrieval system”. It is based on two fundamental ideas: the first one, the TF above mentioned; the second one, proposed by Jones [1972], define, for simple word systems, that the exhaustivity of a document description is the terms it includes, and that the specificity of a term is the number of documents it belongs to.

This assumption completes the TF metric with the frequency with which the term appears in all the documents in the corpus. In this way, words that are very common in all the documents lose some relevance, while the rarer ones are given more importance because they are more characteristic of the document.

The TF-IDF is calculated according to Eq.2.1, where the weighted value of a term t in document d is calculated by multiplying the frequency of the term in the document by the inverse document frequency. The idf is defined as the logarithm of the number of the documents in the corpus (N) divided by the number of document where t occur (df_t).

$$w_{t,d} = tf_{t,d} \times \log\left(\frac{N}{df_t}\right) \quad (2.1)$$

Chapter 3

Static Topic-based Document Representations

Topic modeling is an unsupervised method for deducing topics in a document or in a set of documents. The main challenge with being unsupervised is that the topics are unknown. Therefore, these techniques group words that represent the same topic. They also identify the documents in which that topic is present. The core idea of topic modeling is to extract from the documents in the corpus document-topic and topic-term matrices.

Due to the peculiarities of the project, different types of topic modeling techniques have been studied. We have explored token-based models, models that explore the correlation of topics and embedding-based models. All the models discussed can be observed in the table 3.1.

Token-based topic models
LSA (Deerwester et al. [1990]) pLSA (Hofmann [1999]) LDA (Blei et al. [2001]; Blei et al. [2003]; Hoffman et al. [2010])
Correlated topic models
CTM (Blei and Lafferty [2006a]) HDP (Teh et al. [2006])
Embedding-based topic models
ETM (Dieng et al. [2019a]) Top2vec (Angelov [2020]) BERTopic (Grootendorst [2022])

Table 3.1: Topic models reviewed in this chapter.

3.1 Token-based topic models

In this section, the relevant term-based methods are discussed. They have been the base for developing the current methods and approaches. They became widely used

in the past, and some are still in use today. Their main characteristic was that they did not take into account the semantic meaning of the words. They only looked at statistics and the frequency of occurrence of the words in the texts. In many cases, this led to the generation of artificial topics, a term commonly assigned in literature to topics without meaning.

3.1.1 Latent Semantic Analysis

Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) (Deerwester et al. [1990]) is a non probabilistic model which works over the term-document matrix. The values of this matrix can be calculated with TF or, more commonly, with TF-IDF. The main goal of LSA is to discover a low-rank approximation to the term-document matrix. The hyperparameter K (desired number of topics) provides the final term-document matrix dimensionality. The approximating matrix is built by applying singular value decomposition (SVD) to the term-document matrix. In this way, the similarity structure between columns is maintained and the dimensionality is reduced. As a result of applying SVD, two matrices are obtained: document-topic matrix and term-topic matrix. The new matrices can be used to compare documents, find polysemy and synonymy or to extract the topics of the documents.

Although LSA is fast and easy to implement, it is not currently a convenient option. It is a linear model, it assumes that the terms in the documents follow a Gaussian distribution, the vectors are not interpretable, and it requires large corpus and vocabulary to generate accurate results.

3.1.2 Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis

Probabilistic Latent Semantic Analysis (pLSA) (Hofmann [1999]), also called aspect model (Hofmann et al. [1998]), is an improvement of the above LSA. The main objective of pLSA is to address the problem from a statistical approach instead of a linear algebra approach. This approach departs from the dimensionality reduction methods and focused in probabilistic modeling, being the first case of probabilistic methods for topic identification. It builds a generative model of the documents in the corpus and fits it using probabilistic methods.

During training, the model generates the topic probabilities for each document in the corpus. This is the reason of the main two problems of pLSA:

- It is not a good generative model. It cannot work with documents that have not been part of the learning.
- The more documents in the corpus, the more parameters are estimated, leading to overfitting problems.

3.1.3 Latent Dirichlet Allocation

Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei et al. [2001]; Blei et al. [2003]) is a generative probabilistic model for discrete data. It follows the probabilistic approach and is the first method that models topic semantics using the Bayesian statistical paradigm. LDA is a three-level hierarchical Bayesian model where each text in the corpus is represented as a finite mixture of hidden topics. Nowadays is one of the most used topic modeling techniques (Lancichinetti et al. [2015]).

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The generative model assumes that documents are a mixture of topics and that the structure of these topics is latent (the true topic is unknown). To infer the structure of these topics the topic modeling algorithm uses the term-document matrix. Finally, the algorithm will produce the document-topic and topic-term matrices.

On the one hand, the first main difference between LDA and pLSA, introduced by Blei et al. [2003], is the perplexity of both techniques in predicting new documents. In this comparison, LDA proves to be superior in generating an accurate, low-dimensional, generic semantic representation. Moreover, it should be noted that the dimensional difference between LDA and pLSA is because LDA solves the overfitting problem that pLSA suffered.

On the other hand, there are more differences between LDA and pLSA, as evidenced by the study of Marqas et al. [2020]. This study shows that although LDA and pLSA perform similarly on several tasks, there are some differences. In particular, LDA performs better than pLSA on text categorisation tasks when the topic-document distribution is a low-dimensional representation

One of the main disadvantages of LDA is that it does not allow continuous learning. To solve this, Hoffman et al. [2010] proposes an online variational Bayes algorithm for LDA. Thus, the model can be updated with new documents for online training. The tests carried out by the authors show that the algorithm achieves results as good or better as with other methods in a shorter amount of time.

3.2 Correlated topic models

Topic modeling techniques are good tools for the statistical analysis of texts. However, they are not able to model correlations. Therefore, there are different models that focus on modeling these relationships between topics. The topic correlation can be a very important factor in some situations. This is especially relevant in those cases where the presence of one topic can affect the presence of the others. In this way, it is possible to detect if there are topics that, because they appear together frequently, are correlated. Or the opposite, because they never appear together they have very low correlation and may be mutually exclusive.

3.2.1 Correlated Topic Model

In order to improve the limitations of LDA in modeling the relationships between topics, Blei and Lafferty [2006a] developed Correlated Topic Models (CTM). In CTM the relationships between topics are based on the logistic normal distribution. CTM offers a more natural way to visualise and explore unstructured data sets. However, it requires more training time.

3.2.2 Hierarchical Dirichlet Process

Hierarchical Dirichlet Process (HDP) was presented by Teh et al. [2006]. It does not need an estimation of the latent topics present in the corpus. It is a non-parametric Bayesian model that applies the Dirichlet Process mixture models. The model assumes that observations are made on a set of information. These observations are made on groups within the information set, and each observation is an extraction

from a mixture model. Also, the mixture components are shared between the different groups. In this way, HDP learns the suitable number of mixture components for a dataset.

3.3 Embeddings-based topic models

Classical methods do not take into account the semantic meaning of words. This may lead to artificial topics with words without relation to each other. In this section, the methods that not only evaluate the co-occurrence of words (word-context matrix) but also the semantic correlation between words, are evaluated.

3.3.1 Topic Modeling in Embedding Spaces

Classic topic models are not capable of learning interpretable topics while working with large vocabularies. To deal with this problem Dieng et al. [2019a] developed the Embedded Topic Model (ETM).

ETM is a generative model that combines topic modeling with embeddings. It uses embedding representations for words and topics. It has two latent dimensions. One for embedding the vocabulary in an L dimensional space. The other one for representing each document as a number K of latent topics. In traditional topic modeling, a topic was a distribution over the entire vocabulary of the corpus. However, in ETM, a topic is a vector in the embedding space.

Due to this definition of topics, the way of assigning words to topics has been modified. ETM calculates the correspondence between word embedding and topic embedding. ETM employs a log-linear model to take the inner product of the word embedding matrix and the topic embedding. In this way, the probability of a word being assigned to a topic is due to the agreement between word embedding and topic embedding.

The authors show that ETM uses continuous representations of words and outperforms LDA in topic quality and predictive performance. ETM can find interpretable topics even when working with long vocabularies with stopwords and rare words.

3.3.2 Top2vec

Based on semantic space idea, Angelov [2020] developed top2vec. In contrast to classical methods, top2vec neither needs to know the number of topics nor to preprocess the texts. It avoids using topic estimation techniques, stopwords lists, stemming and lemmatization. Moreover, topic vectors are embedded together with document vectors and word vectors to represent semantic similarity by calculating the distance in the semantic space.

Top2vec assumes that the semantic space is a continuous representation of topics. Furthermore, each point (document) in this semantic space is defined by its nearest words. Thus, points (documents) in this semantic space close to each other will have a similar underlying topic. Top2vec assumes that both topics and terms belong to the same vector space.

To identify the number of topics, top2vec applies the following process. They apply the dimensionality reduction algorithm Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection

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for Dimension Reduction (UMAP) to reduce the document vector sparsity. In this way, it is easier to recognise clusters of documents by density-based clustering. In their work, they apply the Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN) algorithm for this task.

3.3.3 BERTopic

BERTopic is a topic modeling technique developed by Grootendorst [2022]. This technique addresses the topic modeling task as a clustering task.

First, BERTopic generates embeddings of documents with transformer-based pre-trained language models. It uses the Sentence-BERT (SBERT) framework to use pre-trained language models. With these models the dense vector representations are generated from the documents texts. The embeddings are only used to cluster the semantically similar documents and not to generate the topics.

Secondly, it groups the embeddings generated in the previous step. The problem is that the dimensionality of the vectors is too large. To reduce it, BERTopic applies UMAP before performing the clustering. Once the dimensionality of the embeddings has been reduced, the HDBSCAN clustering algorithm is applied.

Finally, the third and last step is to generate the representation of the topics. BERTopic assumes that the clusters generated in the previous step correspond to the topics present in the corpus. The words present in all the documents of the cluster are taken into account to know which are the most representative of the topic. In this way, all the documents in the cluster are considered as a single document and c-TF-IDF, a class-based variation of TF-IDF, is applied to it. With c-TF-IDF, the importance of words in a cluster is evaluated. By applying c-TF-IDF iteratively, the number of topics can be reduced to the user-specified amount.

The c-TF-IDF is calculated according to Eq.3.1, where the weighted value of a term t in class c is calculated by multiplying the frequency of the term in the class by the inverse class frequency. The inverse class frequency is defined as the logarithm of the number of words per class A divided by the frequency of t through all classes (tf_t). To obtain only positive results, a one is added to the division.

$$w_{t,c} = tf_{t,c} \times \log\left(1 + \frac{A}{tf_t}\right) \quad (3.1)$$

Although BERTopic is not essentially a time-based technique, it is capable of analyzing the evolution of topics over time. First, BERTopic is fitted with the complete corpus without temporal distinctions. Thus, the general topics of the corpus are captured. Once the model is fitted, a local representation of a topic can be created by multiplying the term frequency of documents in the timestamp i with its pre-calculated global IDF value (Eq. 3.2).

$$w_{t,c,i} = tf_{t,c,i} \times \log\left(1 + \frac{A}{tf_t}\right) \quad (3.2)$$

Chapter 4

Dynamic Topic-based Document Representations

The topic modeling techniques mentioned above cover many use cases. However, they cannot deal with the evolution of topics over time. Therefore, this section covers modifications to previous models and the new models developed focusing on this particular task. In the state-of-the-art, models capable of dealing with this problem are considered dynamic topic models. All the models discussed in this section can be observed in the table 4.1.

Time-based topic models
DTM (Blei and Lafferty [2006b])
TOT (Wang and McCallum [2006])
dHDP (Ren et al. [2008])
cDTM (Wang et al. [2012])
D-ETM (Dieng et al. [2019b])

Table 4.1: Topic models reviewed in this section.

4.1 Dynamic Topic Model

Blei and Lafferty [2006b] presented Dynamic Topic Model (DTM) to analyze the temporal evolution of topics. DTM is the first and most common dynamic topic model (Dieng et al. [2019b]). DTM is based on the underlying principles of LDA. Traditional models assume that documents are drawn from the same set of topics. However, the order of the documents reveals the evolution of the topic. DTM is a probabilistic model that allows to analyze the evolution of topics over time. It assumes that the information is divided by time slices. For this purpose, the documents are modelled to make the topics of time slice t evolution of time slice $t-1$.

It is also known as the discrete Dynamic Topic Model (dDTM) because it is a sequential topic model for discrete data (Wang et al. [2012]). DTM assumes that the topic evolution is governed by a discrete time-space. However, is unable to identify how topics appear or disappear over time.

DTM discretizes time into several periods and applies LDA to each period to model the documents. Therefore, it is also known as D-LDA (Dieng et al. [2019b]). Although it is a powerful model, the complexity of variational inference increases as the granularity increases.

4.2 Topics Over Time

Wang and McCallum [2006] presented Topics over Time (TOT), a Non-Markov Continuous-Time Model of Topical Trends. TOT is an LDA-like model that, in addition to capturing the structure of the information, also captures how it evolves. It assumes that the temporal spaces are continuous, contrary to DTM, which assumes as discrete.

Assumes that the meaning of a topic is constant, but its occurrence and relationships change over time. In other words, topics and their meanings are modelled as constants over time and TOT only captures changes in topic co-occurrence. It is not able to capture changes in topic word distributions.

Topic modeling is carried out by considering word co-occurrence and temporal information. In this way, it is allowed to identify patterns over time and thus predict the date of a document or predict the distribution of topics in a temporal interval. When TOT detects a strong co-occurrence relationship between words in time-space and then disappears, TOT will create a topic with a narrow temporal distribution. However, if the co-occurrence persists over time, TOT will create a topic with a wide temporal distribution.

TOT parameterizes a continuous distribution in time associated with each topic. This avoids discretization and the granularity choice problem. The parameterization focuses on discovering topics that capture word co-occurrence and patterns over time.

4.3 Dynamic hierarchical Dirichlet process

Dynamic hierarchical Dirichlet process (dHDP) was proposed by Ren et al. [2008]. The dHDP is an extension of HDP that includes time dependence. It was developed to model the time-evolving statistical properties of sequential data sets. The statistical properties are linked by a parameter that controls their probabilistic similarity.

4.4 Continuous Time Dynamic Topic Modeling

Continuous Time Dynamic Topic Modeling (cDTM) was developed by Wang et al. [2012]. The cDTM is an extension of DTM that does not require time discretization. It is a dynamic topic model that uses Brownian motion to model the underlying topics in a corpus. Like DTM, cDTM assumes that topics are a pattern of words that evolve. However, it assumes that the evolution of topics takes place in arbitrary periods. Like TOT, it assumes that the temporal spaces are continuous. The authors comment that cDTM can be seen as the granularity limiting process of DTM.

The main advantage of cDTM is that sparse variational inference can be used for fast model comparison. In addition, cDTM is capable of predicting timestamps.

4.5 Dynamic topic Modeling in Embedding Spaces

Dynamic Topic Modeling in Embedding Spaces (D-ETM) is a generative model that combines DTM and ETM. It was developed by Dieng et al. [2019b] and combines word-embeddings with the temporal representation of topics.

Like DTM, D-ETM allows topics to vary over time, which is the main difference from ETM. However, each topic is a time-varying vector over the word embeddings space. Using word embeddings allows D-ETM to generalize better than DTM and improve the topics. Experiments conducted by the authors show how D-ETM outperforms DTM in predictive performance and topic quality, in addition to requiring less time.

D-ETM forms distributions over the vocabulary with word and topic embeddings. The probability of a term being in a topic is high when the topic vector and term vector match. Therefore, words with similar semantic meanings will belong to the same topic because they are close in semantic space. Because D-ETM learns topics according to a semantic space, it can work with words that do not exist in the corpus. It will assign an unknown word to the topic with the highest semantic correlation.

Chapter 5

Performance Metrics

The unsupervised nature and semantics of the topic models makes choosing one over the other difficult. Some tasks like document classification allow performance evaluation. However, they are not universal metrics. For evaluating the quality of topics, several metrics have been developed over the last 15 years. This section will discuss the most important ones.

5.1 Perplexity

One of the first efforts to evaluate topic models was in terms of their perplexity. This idea was introduced by Wallach et al. [2009]. In their work, they state that held-out probability is a metric that allows measuring the performance of topic models. This metric estimates the probability with documents that the model has not previously seen. Thus, the best model will be the one with the highest probability of held-out documents.

In other words, this metric measures how well the model can generalize. This metric is usually calculated using the normalized log-likelihood of a held-out test set. The main problem with this metric is that being a statistical evaluation, it does not allow for assessing whether the topic is coherent or not.

5.2 UCI

One of the first metrics that focused on evaluating the quality of semantics of learned topics is UCI. This metric was introduced by Newman et al. [2010]. UCI treats the whole corpus as a meta-document and scores all word pairs by term co-occurrence. It calculates the pointwise mutual information (PMI) for each word pair. Then, it uses a sliding window of size 10 to identify the co-occurrence. Finally, the arithmetic mean of the PMI values is the coherence of the generated topics.

5.3 NPMI

NPMI, introduced by Aletras and Stevenson [2013], is an extension of UCI that uses Normalised PMI (NPMI).

5.4 C_V

Röder et al. [2015] presented C_V as the best performing metric compared to others, including those mentioned above. This metric combines the indirect cosine measure with the NPMI and the sliding window. However, the authors state that the sliding window has to be of a larger size than the one used in UCI to achieve better performance.

C_V calculates the cooccurrence of words of the same topic in a sliding window. These calculations are used to compute the NPMI of each headword with respect to the other top words in the topic. This process returns a series of vectors. Finally, with the cosine they calculate the similarity. In this way, the coherence is calculated by averaging the similarities.

5.5 UMass

UMass is a metric based on the co-occurrence of words in the corpus. It was introduced by Mimno et al. [2011] and, unlike perplexity, claims that having a held-out corpus is not necessary to evaluate topics.

UMass assumes that words that speak of related topics coexist frequently in texts. Meanwhile, words that have no semantic relationship will rarely coexist in texts. Thus, the score is defined based on the co-occurrence of words in documents. Words that co-occur frequently are evaluated positively.

Chapter 6

Evaluation

In this section, the technical decisions made to carry out this project are explained. It explains the corpus used, the criteria for data preprocessing, the resources available in the system, and how the implementation was carried out.

6.1 Corpus

The COVID-19 Open Research Dataset (CORD-19) presented by Wang et al. [2020] was used. CORD-19 contains a mixture of articles and preprints on COVID-19 and similar past coronaviruses like SARS and MERS. This resource was developed as an initiative to bring together the machine learning community with experts in the biomedical domain to identify effective treatments and management policies for COVID19. The CORD19 release used was the June 2, 2022 release. This version contains 401,214 papers.

6.2 Data preparation

Inspired by the guidelines of Maier et al. [2018], these steps have been followed for the text preprocessing:

1. Due to the available resources and the large number of articles, it has been decided to work only with the abstracts of the articles. In this way, the computational cost of this phase was reduced. Considering the small number of articles that did not have abstracts, it was decided to discard them and not take them into account. In addition, there are papers in the corpus with publication dates later than the corpus version. Given the distortion that these articles can generate in the models, it has been decided not to take them into account. Thus, only previously published articles are used.
2. The corpus contains articles in several languages. The main language is English, so it was decided to filter the articles to use only those written in English. The *Langdetect* package was used to identify the language of the texts.
3. The text has been lowercased in order to group terms by character and not by their format. Observing the content of the abstracts, some DOI links have been

found, therefore, and before carrying out the following steps, all the links have been deleted.

4. All stopwords present in the texts have been removed. The list of stopwords has been extracted from the repository *stopwords-iso*¹. In this repository, stopwords from different sources have been collected in order to create a list as extensive as possible.
5. Punctuation characters and all numbers have been removed. For punctuation characters, the list provided by the python package *String* has been used. However, due to the particularity of healthcare texts, single hyphens have not been removed.
6. A minimum word size criteria has been defined in order to eliminate acronyms and abbreviations which are difficult to interpret and use out of context. To this end, the decision has been taken to eliminate all words with less than 4 letters.
7. The remaining words after the previous steps are lemmatized. It has been decided to use lemmatization and not stemming because in this way, the final result is more easily interpretable. The *WordNetLemmatizer* from the *Nltk* package has been used for this task.
8. Due to the size of the corpus, it has been assumed that, on the one hand, there will be words that, due to their high frequency in the documents, are common in the corpus and do not provide any significant value to the topics. On the other hand, there will be words that, due to their low frequency in the documents, are irrelevant. For this reason, pruning parameters of the maximum frequency of 80% and minimum frequency of 0.1% have been established. The pruning is performed based on the frequency of a term relative to the volume of all the words in the corpus. This task has been carried out using the *CountVectorizer* of the *Sklearn* package.
9. Similar to the minimum word size criteria, a minimum text size criterion has been established. The objective is to filter out all texts that have a number of words below a threshold, in order to filter out texts of a very general nature, full of stopwords, common words in the corpus, acronyms, etc. For this project a minimum text size of 5 words has been established.

6.3 System

Due to the high demand of resources of these models and the preprocessing of the data, a high performance computing (Supercomputing) service has been used. This service is provided by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid through the Centro de Supercomputación y Visualización de Madrid (CeSViMa) using the Magerit-3 supercomputer. Magerit-3 uses *Slurm*², a workload manager that allows to allocate the needed resources for the execution of the jobs. The resources available on the supercomputer are summarized in the table 6.1.

¹<https://github.com/stopwords-iso/stopwords-iso>

²<https://github.com/SchedMD/slurm/releases/tag/slurm-20-11-7-1>

Magerit-3	
Operating System	CentOS Linux release 8.3.2011
Processor	Intel Xeon Gold 6230 2.1 GHz
Architecture	64-bits
RAM	Up to 192GB
Cores	Up to 600 cores
Maximum work duration	Up to 160 hours
Disk	480 GB of SSD
Accelerators	4 × NVIDIA A100 2 × NVIDIA V100

Table 6.1: Available resources in Magerit-3.

6.4 Implementation

Of the previously identified models, the ones that best meet the requirements of the problem are DTM, DETM and BERTopic. This is because the key features of this project is to analyze the evolution of topics over time. Although analyzing the correlation of different topics is something that brings great value to the field, those models are not able to deal with the evolution of topics and the evolution of relationships between topics.

The implementation of these models required the use of different software packages:

- To use the DTM model, the implementation available in the *Gensim 4.2.0v* package³ has been explored. However, after performing several tests, a serious problem was identified in this implementation. The time and resources required to train the model were too high. This problem has been identified in the open issue #1545⁴ and, although there is an attempt to fix it in the open pull request #3172⁵, it has not yet been resolved.

Because of this, it has been decided to use the wrapper available in older versions of the *Gensim* package, *Gensim 3.8.3v* package⁶. This wrapper allowed to use from Python the original code of the DTM model⁷, developed by the authors of the paper in the C language. In this way, it is possible to train the model with fewer resources and in a shorter amount of time. Moreover, in order to use it, the source code required manual compilation.

- For the DETM model, tests have been performed with the original code of the implementation developed by the authors⁸. However, there is a fork of the original repository where several runtime errors are fixed and, in addition, there are several scripts to visualize the results⁹. The scripts for preparing the input data

³<https://github.com/RaRe-Technologies/gensim/releases/tag/4.2.0>

⁴<https://github.com/RaRe-Technologies/gensim/issues/1545>

⁵<https://github.com/RaRe-Technologies/gensim/pull/3172>

⁶<https://github.com/RaRe-Technologies/gensim/releases/tag/3.8.3>

⁷<https://github.com/blei-lab/dtm>

⁸<https://github.com/adjidieng/DETM>

⁹<https://github.com/quynhneo/detm>

have been modified to be able to work with the corpus and, the visualization scripts to be able to visualize the topics better.

- To use the BERTopic model, the *Bertopic 0.11.0v* library¹⁰, developed by the author of the paper, has been used. This python library allows to implement the model and use it in a simple way.

Although several metrics were discussed in the previous section, to evaluate the models, the coherence values C_V and UMass will be taken into account. These two metrics will be used to measure the quality of the topics generated by the models in terms of semantic quality (interpretability) and co-occurrence of the words in the topics (specificity). With C_V the semantic quality of the topics is computed and with UMass the frequency with which the words of each topic coexist in the corpus documents is calculated. To use these metrics the *Gensim 4.2.0v* package has been used. This package implements the coherences presented in the *Palmetto* framework of Röder et al. [2015].

The *Weights & Biases 0.13.2v*¹¹ package has been used to record the experiments and tests performed. WB is a machine learning platform that allows to develop models in a efficient way. From all the functionalities that this tool offers, only the system resources logger and the online platform to visualize the data have been used.

¹⁰<https://github.com/MaartenGr/BERTopic/releases/tag/v0.11.0>

¹¹<https://github.com/wandb/wandb/releases/tag/v0.13.2>

Chapter 7

Results and conclusions

7.1 Data Preprocessing

Data preprocessing is one of the most critical processes when generating topic models. It is important to remove as much noise as possible while keeping the relevant terms. The more words that are removed, the faster, more efficient and more correct the models will be.

As mentioned above, the corpus used is the June 2, 2022 release of CORD-19. CORD-19 is a corpus from the biomedical domain which contains a mixture of articles and preprints on COVID-19 and similar past coronaviruses like SARS and MERS.

The information available for each article is as follows: title, authors, abstract, text, bibliographic entries, internal references (tables, figures or elements within the article with their respective title) and acknowledgements. In addition to this information, the following metadata is also available for each paper: the source from which it originates, its doi, the license of use, its date of publication and the journal in which was published.

After applying the preprocessing steps to the 401,214 papers in the corpus, only 245,476 were usable. The majority were discarded because they did not satisfy the minimum text size requirement after processing. The rest were excluded because they had no abstract or they are written in other language. In the end, preprocessing eliminates many terms, and several documents do not keep the defined minimum size required.

This task took 5 days, 17 hours and 45 minutes to complete with 160GB of RAM allocated. The distribution of the articles by date can be seen in image 7.1. In this image, it can be seen how 88% of the papers belong to the period 2020-2022. This may affect the construction of the topics.

In order to measure the impact of SARS-CoV-2 on the coronavirus literature, it is necessary to know which events and drugs are related to it. The drugs that appear on the living guidelines for COVID-19 set by WHO¹ will be used. This list contains recommendations for the use or non-use of different drugs and treatments. From this list we will take the different SARS-CoV-2 related drugs which will be used in the evaluation of the models.

¹<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-therapeutics-2022.4>

We collected the context-stopwords in a resource available from Zenodo². Some of the context-stopwords appear in the living guidelines for COVID-19 set by WHO. An example of this are the following words:

- The drug *nirmatrelvir-ritonavir*. It appears nine times in the corpus documents. On April 22, 2022, WHO strongly recommended the use of this drug in patients with a non-severe disease with an increased risk of hospitalization³. This word, which is important in this paper, has been removed because of its low appearance in the corpus. Perhaps, in future versions of the corpus, this word will appear more times and will not be removed.
- Elements related to *remdesivir*. On November 20, 2020, the WHO launches a conditional recommendation for the use of *remdesivir* in patients with non-severe COVID-19 with increased risk of hospitalization⁴. Although the list of filtered words does not include *remdesivir* on its own, there are compound words with this term. In the word list, there are 40 terms with the word *remdesivir*. From all of them, the most repeated word is *remdesivir-tp*, a variation of *remdesivir* that appears 15 times in the corpus documents.
- The drug *molnupiravir*. On March 3, 2022, the WHO issued a conditional recommendation for the use of this drug in patients with non-severe COVID-19 at increased risk of hospitalization (excluding pregnant or breastfeeding women and children)⁵. This drug is listed because it appears only 87 times in the corpus documents. However, it is possible that in future versions of the corpus this word will be dropped from the list if it appears in more papers.

There are probably more terms in this list with an impact on this work. The problem is that the list is composed of 362,406 terms, which makes it difficult to analyze and evaluate the impact on the work.

Figure 7.1: Distribution of papers in the corpus according to their publication date.

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129601>

³<https://app.magicapp.org/guideline/nBkO1E/rec/LwrMyv>

⁴<https://app.magicapp.org/guideline/nBkO1E/rec/nBMO8R>

⁵<https://app.magicapp.org/guideline/nBkO1E/rec/E85WNb>

7.2 Performance analysis

This section explains how the different models have been built, their coherence and the resources needed for their creation. Each model has its challenges when it comes to be implemented. Some models are simpler due to the few parameters required for their implementation. However, this simplicity can affect their performance.

The performance, as mentioned above, will be analyzed based on the coherence metrics C_V and $UMass$ especially over the last five years. The aim is to measure how the coherence of the model evolved over these years and if it is stable. Thus, we will see the quality of the generated dynamic topics. In addition, the resources used in its execution and the time taken, will also be mentioned.

There are two points to be explained. The first is that a topic is composed by the 15 words with the highest relevance. The second one is that all the parameters of the models listed below have been chosen by empirical method until the best results were obtained.

7.2.1 DTM

As mentioned above, the wrapper allows making use of the original DTM model from *Python*. The implementation of the DTM algorithm used in our experiments was downloaded from the original *github* repository and compiled to be used in the Magerit-3 system. The parameters chosen for training the model were the following:

- Number of topics to be generated: **100**
- Minimum iterations of the LDA models: **6**
- Maximum iterations of the LDA models: **20**
- Maximum EM iterations of the LDA models: **10**
- Dirichlet distribution concentration: **0.01**
- **0.005** as the hyperparameter that controls the evolution speed of the topics during the timeslices.

This model is not optimized for GPU acceleration, which implies that the model is trained by CPU. This affects the model performance significantly, requiring a greater amount of time. This model does not require much RAM to train. The model has used around 13GB only. The training required 43 hours and 7 minutes, giving positive results. The coherence C_V is 0.692, while the coherence $UMass$ is 3.889 for the 2022 topics.

As explained above, the coherence of the model topics will be tracked over the last five years. Thereby, it is possible to verify that the topic evolution is robust and that the coherence of the model is stable. As can be seen in the table 7.1, the coherences C_V and $UMass$ do not differ much in the last five years. This is an indicator of the optimal evolution of the topics over the years, and that the model can correctly represent the content of the corpus across them. This means that the model is robust.

Model	Year	C_V	UCI	NPMI	UMass
DTM	2022	0.692	2.556	0.229	3.889
	2021	0.725	2.724	0.252	3.743
	2020	0.725	2.801	0.255	3.739
	2019	0.710	2.803	0.246	3.834
	2018	0.724	2.803	0.260	3.592

Table 7.1: DTM model coherences for different dates.

7.2.2 BERTopic

As explained above, BERTopic is not a model specially designed to deal with the evolution of topics. Unlike the other models, BERTopic does not generate the topics of a time slice as an evolution of the previous time slice topics. Instead, BERTopic generates the topics for the last time slice, and from this trained model, it generates the topics for each time slice. The generation of the topics for the previous time slices is done by generating c-TF-IDF representations for each time slice and, subsequently, averaging them with the global c-TF-IDF representations.

The following parameters have been chosen to create the BERTopic model:

- Number of topics to be generated: **100**
- Sentence transformer to be used by the model: **all-MiniLM-L6-v2**⁶

The model generated from this configuration is good. It achieves 0.709 of C_V coherence and 2.770 of $UMass$. The model has been trained for 5 hours and 21 minutes, using about 25GB of RAM to achieve this performance.

Nevertheless, values differ when generating the dynamic topic modeling from this model. The BERTopic model with dynamic topic modeling achieves 0.716 of C_V coherence and 2.336 of $UMass$ for the 2022 topics. The coherence C_V is high and implies that the topics generated in 2022 represent adequately the corpus documents. In contrast, the $UMass$ value is low. This implies that the words in the topics do not co-appear frequently in the texts. To increase the $UMass$ value, a higher number of topics would have to be defined. In this way, the topics will be more specific, and the words that appear in them will appear more frequently.

However, more specific topics have certain drawbacks. First, the resources needed to train the model increase. The required amount of memory and the time for training would increase, which, combined with the execution restrictions could stop models from being trained above a certain threshold of topics. Secondly, having a larger number of topics can lead to the generation of artificial topics or topics with similar words, with no meaning and introducing noise in the model.

Due to the method used by BERTopic to generate dynamic topics, the C_V and $UMass$ metrics may not be very representative. After all, BERTopic can generate good topics but may not be able to create a good evolution of them. The problem is that BERTopic does not generate the probability distribution of topic words for each time slice, only for the last one. Because of this, it is impossible to know in detail the evolution of the words, making it difficult to analyze the generated topics. Therefore, measur-

⁶<https://huggingface.co/sentence-transformers/all-MiniLM-L6-v2>

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ing BERTopic’s ability to generate dynamic topics is complicated, and it would be convenient to analyze the coherence in other time slices.

In this work the corpus has been grouped by years. Therefore, the time slices for which BERTopic generates the dynamic topic modeling are the different years in which the articles of the corpus have been published. The coherence for the last five years topics has been evaluated to measure BERTopic’s ability to generate the dynamic topics. The values are shown in the table 7.2.

Model	Year	C_V	UCI	NPMI	UMass
BERTopic	2022	0.716	1.560	0.176	2.336
	2021	0.714	1.557	0.175	2.366
	2020	0.710	1.523	0.173	2.360
	2019	0.469	-1.475	0.012	5.042
	2018	0.439	-1.689	-0.006	5.163

Table 7.2: BERTopic model coherences for different dates.

As can be seen from the results obtained, the evolution of the topics is inconsistent. When going back three years, the C_V coherence drops a lot and the *UMass* coherence increases. This implies that BERTopic loses the ability to generate good topic evolution. Reached a date, 2019, it seems that BERTopic values the co-occurrence of terms in a topic more than the semantic quality of the topic. This phenomenon is closely related to the factor discussed in the data preprocessing section 7.1, 88% of the documents belong to the 2020-2022 period.

BERTopic can represent topics with high interpretability for most of the documents in the corpus. But, it seems incapable of covering the entire corpus.

7.2.3 DETM

The DETM model is the most challenging evaluated model for this work. First, the parameters and methods needed to generate the embeddings for the corpus vocabulary. Secondly, preparation of the corpus documents to use them in the model. And thirdly, the parameters for training the model. All these configurable elements make achieving a model with optimal results a complicated task that requires precision in all its phases.

On the one hand, the generation of the embeddings. Two different approaches have been used. The first one is by training a word2vec model and generating the vectors for each word of the vocabulary with it. The second is by retraining a language model with the corpus texts and generating the vectors for each vocabulary word with it.

On the other hand, the data preparation has been done from the script available as an example by the authors of the model with some modifications for its use. Finally, the training has been performed as in any other neural network, by studying the impact of the parameters and adjusting them to achieve a good result.

7.2.3.1 Embeddings with Word2vec

As mentioned above, the *gensim* library has been used to generate the word2vec model. The parameters selected to train this model have been the following:

- Dimensions of the embeddings to be generated: **300**
- Skip-gram window size: **10**
- Negative sampling: **15**
- Initial learning rate: **0.12**
- **0.001** as the minimum value that alpha can reach (since it decreases during training).
- Iterations to be performed on the corpus: **50**

In addition, the word2vec model allows speeding of the training by parallelization. Therefore, to reduce the training time, eight processor cores have been assigned to the training. The training of this model was completed in less than 17 minutes and used about 18GB of RAM.

7.2.3.2 Embeddings with Deberta

The following parameters have been used to retrain the previously downloaded BERT model :

- Dimensions of the embeddings to be generated: **768** (default value in the BERT architecture)
- Pre-trained BERT model: **microsoft/deberta-base**
- Maximum number of documents per batch to retrain the model: **100000**
- Maximum number of tokens that can be represented by the model (vocabulary size): **30522**.

With this configuration, the model took 9 minutes to finish the training using only about 21GB of RAM. It was possible to use GPU acceleration, but it was not considered necessary. Only the CPU has been used due to the short time needed to complete the task.

7.2.3.3 Document processing

The preprocessing performed above has prepared the data for being used. However, to use the data in this model, it is necessary to change its format and create the train, test and validation sets. For this, it was not necessary to configure many parameters, only the size of the train, test and validation sets, which are the following:

- Documents for the train set: **85%**
- Documents for the test set: **10%**
- Documents for the validation set: **5%**

To avoid the training set being filled with very recent documents and choosing a few documents from previous years, the percentages of documents are taken from each time slice. This means that for the training set, 85% of the documents of each date are chosen. In the same way, this is done with each set and its corresponding percentage.

This whole process took less than 9 minutes and used about 120GB of RAM.

7.2.3.4 Neural network training

Both embedding generation techniques manage to generate vectors for the 5795 words that exist in the corpus vocabulary. These word vectors are used by the model to generate the topics. To generate the model, apart from the embeddings, other parameters are also needed. The parameters used in the generation of the different models can be seen in the table 7.4.

The main drawback of this model is the error function it uses to update the network weights. The error function is the perplexity. This implies that in each batch iteration, the model evolves to reduce this parameter. However, the perplexity is not a parameter that matters in this work, since the priority is to have topics with high interpretability and as specific as possible. Optimizing perplexity may lead to less good results than would be the case if coherence was optimized.

This training was done using a v100 graphics card and 170GB of RAM. The deberta model took 7 hours and 40 minutes to complete, while the word2vec model took 12 hours and 14 minutes.

The results of the models trained with these parameters are poor. Even though a variety of configurations have been tested, it has not been possible to achieve better results than those shown in the table 7.3.

As can be seen, the generated models have very low interpretability. The model using deberta embeddings has been able to generate topics with higher C_V coherence than those generated by the word2vec trained model. In addition, the topics resulting from the deberta training are more specific, with a much higher coherence $UMass$ than those generated by the other model.

Model	Year	C_V	UCI	NPMI	UMass
Deberta	2022	0.460	-1.594	-0.037	5.241
	2021	0.439	-1.368	-0.029	5.274
	2020	0.443	-1.780	-0.043	5.392
	2019	0.444	-1.708	-0.037	5.797
	2018	0.450	-1.386	-0.026	5.113
word2vec	2022	0.412	-0.060	-0.004	1.671
	2021	0.414	-0.058	-0.004	1.674
	2020	0.418	-0.042	-0.001	1.690
	2019	0.423	-0.027	0.001	1.733
	2018	0.432	0.002	0.005	1.802

Table 7.3: DETM model coherences for different dates.

7.3. Evaluation of model capabilities

Embedding	Parameter	Value
Deberta	Number of words per topic	15
	Number of topics	100
	Learning rate	0.0001
	Learning rate decay factor	False
	Anneal the learning rate	False
	Optimizer	Adam
	L2 regularization	0.012
	Epochs	300
	Batch size	256
	Dimensions of embeddings	768
	Dimensions of rho	300
	Encoder activation function	RELU
	Encoder dropout	0.1
	Encoder dimensions of hidden space	400
	Eta dropout	0.05
	Eta number of layers	4
Prior variance	0.005	
Gradient clipping	2	
Word2vec	Number of words per topic	15
	Number of topics	100
	Learning rate	0.0001
	Learning rate decay factor	4
	Anneal the learning rate	False
	Optimizer	Adam
	L2 regularization	0.0000012
	Epochs	500
	Batch size	200
	Dimensions of embeddings	300
	Dimensions of rho	300
	Encoder activation function	RELU
	Encoder dropout	0.1
	Encoder dimensions of hidden space	400
	Eta dropout	False
	Eta number of layers	4
Prior variance	0.005	
Gradient clipping	2	

Table 7.4: Parameters used to train the DETM models.

7.3 Evaluation of model capabilities

We defined two main tasks to study the capabilities of the topics generated by the different models: the ability to identify events and the ability to contextualize drugs. On the one hand, the objective is to study the evolution of certain words in the topics and to see how they behave in the face of certain events. On the other hand, the objective is to study how certain words are related to each other in the topics.

The corpus includes articles about different viruses of the coronavirus family and the

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diseases caused by them. To analyze the ability to identify events, the SARS epidemic, the MERS virus and COVID-19 will be taken as relevant events. The objective is to analyze how the model captured these events. We also want to see if the model captures them with quality and clarity.

We will take some examples from the WHO list of therapeutic recommendations for COVID-19⁷ to analyze the ability to contextualize drugs. We will analyze whether the models have been able to pick up these drugs in their topics and with which other elements they appear related.

The main restriction of using these models is that cross-referencing the topics is a very challenging task. We defined the following method for cross-referencing the topics of the different models. For each model, a set of words will be manually searched for in all the topics and years. The goal is to find the topic where words have the highest relevance in each model. We will cross-reference the matching topic of each model. We assume that the topic of each model in which the word has the highest probability of belonging represents the same concept, and, therefore, it is the same topic. Thus, we can take the topics of the different models and compare them.

There is a problem with this approach and with the BERTopic model. As mentioned above, BERTopic generates the probabilities of word topic membership only for the last time slice. Because of this, it is not possible to extract the maximum probability of a word belonging to a topic in any of the previous time slices. This has made it necessary to associate the word to one of the topics in the last time slice, even if its importance is less than it has been in others in previous years. Moreover, this implies a fundamental problem: the word in the last time slice may not be among the top 15 words. This would imply that it would be impossible to find a topic for that word. Consequently, it would be assumed that BERTopic has been unable to generate the representation of such a topic.

7.3.1 Ability to identify events

To satisfy the first objective, we have decided to evaluate the ability of the models to identify relevant events by searching for peaks of relevance on coronaviruses. For this purpose, we are going to look for events related to:

- **SARS.** During 2002 and 2004, there was an epidemic due to the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS). This virus has the official name SARS-CoV, now called SARS-CoV-1, to differentiate it from SARS-CoV-2.
- **MERS.** In 2012, a new type of coronavirus, called Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS-CoV), was identified. According to WHO, this virus was an epidemic and pandemic-prone disease⁸.
- **SARS-CoV-2.** At the end of 2019, the first cases of COVID-19, a disease developed by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, were identified. This virus has caused a global pandemic that is still in progress.

These three events are related and should appear in some topic of each model. The ideal outcome would be that these viruses coexist on the same topic. The topic could

⁷<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-therapeutics-2022.4>

⁸<https://www.emro.who.int/pandemic-epidemic-diseases/mers-cov/mers-situation-update-january-2020.html>

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be named the evolution of the coronavirus since all three viruses belong to the coronavirus family.

We have used the following words to search for the topics representing the different events:

- *SARS*: sars, sars-cov y coronavirus.
- *MERS*: middle-east, middle, east, mers, mers-cov, coronavirus.
- *SARS-CoV-2*: covid , covid-, sars-cov-, coronavirus. The words covid- and sars-cov- are used because in preprocessing the numbers have been removed from the text, and they refer to covid-19 and sars-cov-2.

The topics resulting from searching for these events in the different models can be seen in their corresponding graphs: the image 7.2 for the DTM model, the image 7.3, 7.4 and 7.5 for the BERTopic model, the image 7.6 for the DETM deberta model, the image 7.7, 7.8 and 7.9 for the DETM deberta model.

The first thing to note about the results shown is how the BERTopic data has been displayed. Since we do not have the probabilities for each word in each time slice, we have taken the rank of that word in the top fifteen words as an element to determine its position. The words with the highest value will be the ones that appear above the others at the top.

In the graphs, showing all the words of the topic in each year made them less interpretable. Therefore, we decided to take the x top words of the years shown and display only the progression of this reduced number of words. In the case of DTM, the five top words of the topic for the last 22 years have been taken. With BERTopic, due to the difficulty of comprehension, it has been decided to reduce this number to three. In the case of DETM, the top four words have been used to ease its interpretation.

7.3.1.1 DTM

Figure 7.2: Interpretation of the DTM model, coronavirus evolution.

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The conclusions drawn from the DTM's ability to identify events are the following:

- **SARS, MERS and COVID-19.** Of all the models, DTM was the only one capable of capturing the evolution of the coronavirus with precision and quality. It can be perfectly observed how the topic words evolve continuously. Top words do not change rapidly, and trends and events can be identified.

Coronavirus was the main topic until the SARS-CoV-1 epidemic began. The SARS-CoV-1 trend continues until 2012 when MERS appears and starts to gain relevance within the topic. In addition, next to this topic appear the words middle and east, which follow the same shape as mers. This is because this word is called Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus.

With the entry at the end of 2019 of COVID-19, the importance of mers declines and SARS-CoV-2 appears and grows. SARS-CoV-2 becomes the most important word in the topic almost as soon as it appears. In addition, words related to vaccine research, such as spike and protein, appear together with SARS-CoV-2.

The DTM results are very good and agree with the coherence values obtained in the performance analysis. The interpretability of the topic is very high and it is not difficult to understand its evolution.

7.3.1.2 BERTopic

Figure 7.3: Interpretation of the BERTopic model, SARS coronavirus evolution.

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The conclusions drawn from the BERTopic's ability to identify events are the following:

- **SARS.** The word SARS appears among the three top words of the BERTopic model in 2005, until then, this word had not entered the top. As soon as it enters, it remains interruptedly at the top until 2022. The re-emergence corresponds slightly with the MERS and SARS-CoV-2 events, although not entirely. Because of the difficulty of interpreting this topic, it is clear that this is not very consistent and seems artificial. In addition, SARS does not seem to be directly related to the word coronavirus. It appears linked to the word cov, but this only appears once in 2007, so this relationship cannot be assumed.
- **MERS.** For BERTopic there is no evolution in the MERS topic. BERTopic has been able to find elements to relate it to, but there is no evolution of the topic according to reality. The model is unable to identify the starting date of the term, and no clear relationship seems to exist with either SARS or the coronavirus. The most obvious relationship is the one with the middle, but it is not sufficient to take this topic as one that represents the virus. We can state that the evolution of this topic is erroneous and artificial.
- **COVID-19.** BERTopic is unable to generate a good interpretation of COVID-19 events. Each year the top words vary, and many move in and out of the top three. We can see a slight evolution in the years 2020 to 2022. However, before the year 2020, they have no evolution at all and appear as simple sets of words. There is no progression in the topic that demonstrates a relationship of COVID with any of the other events.

Moreover, the topic looks like an artificially generated list of words without taking into account the evolution of the topic. This behaviour corresponds to the coherence values obtained. BERTopic generates an interpretable evolution of the topics only in the period 2020-2022.

BERTopic's results are disappointing. The grouping mechanism it performs to generate the dynamic topic modeling does not give good results. The clearest example is the COVID-19 topic. COVID-19 appeared in 2020, so it cannot exist earlier. The problem is that having trained with many documents directly related to COVID-19, BERTopic may have assigned an exclusive topic for this term. That is why, when you go back in time to before it appears, the topic is completely artificial as it has no relationship before that year.

The problem resides in the approach. Generating the topics for the last time slice of the dataset means that in these cases with such unbalanced data, it does not know how to work with outliers. In these cases, the models that generate the topics chronologically can maintain consistency and interpretability during all the time slices.

7.3.1.3 DETM

Topic generated by DETM deberta on SARS prior to COVID-19

Topic generated by DETM deberta on SARS during COVID-19

Figure 7.6: Interpretation of the DETM deberta model, coronavirus evolution.

The conclusions drawn from the DETM deberta’s ability to identify events are the following:

- **MERS.** No terms related to MERS have been found. DETM has been unable to generate a topic related to MERS, which makes it impossible to evaluate the quality of the topic. It is also impossible to compare it with the other models. Because of this, it can be stated that DETM fails to capture the entire evolution of the coronavirus.
- **SARS and COVID-19.** This topic perfectly captures the evolution of the SARS-CoV-1 virus and the emergence of SARS-CoV-2 in 2020. We split the graph in two due to the high relevance of SARS-CoV-2 data volume. Even so, we can see how SARS-CoV-1 appears as the most important element of the topic in the

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2004-2006 interval. Moreover, we can notice how in the year 2020, with the entry of COVID-19, the topic changes completely. All the words on the top are replaced by those related to COVID-19. We can affirm that DETM, even with its low value in coherence, shows that it is moderately capable of analyzing the evolution of the coronavirus topic.

Figure 7.7: Interpretation of the DETM word2vec model, SARS coronavirus evolution.

Figure 7.8: Interpretation of the DETM word2vec model, MERS coronavirus evolution.

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Figure 7.9: Interpretation of the DETM word2vec model, COVID coronavirus evolution.

The conclusions drawn from the DETM word2vec’s ability to identify events are the following:

- **SARS.** The SARS topic is composed of different words from the coronavirus field. We can witness how the topic grows exponentially during the epidemic period, and we can see with which words it is related. First of all, the impact of the words health and disease on the topic is clear. These words remain for many years in the top words and have stable probabilities. In addition, we can observe how in 2020, with SARS-CoV-2, COVID-19 enters the topic. Although it is not the topic of COVID-19, this concept is present in the topic of SARS.
- **MERS.** The MERS topic is difficult to interpret. As before, the impact of COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 affects the topic. The words COVID-19 and pandemic take over the top words from 2021 onwards. As for MERS, we can hardly observe its impact on the topic. It appears during the years 2016 and 2017, which is similar to the events that occurred, but it does not acquire much importance. The words that dominate the topic for the most amount of time are respiratory and virus, which semantically fits with MERS.
- **COVID-19.** The COVID-19 topic does not provide much value in terms of topic evolution. The topic is, at all times, dominated by the word patient. Before 2019 this topic was mainly made up of patient, respiratory, infection and clinical. In 2019, because of COVID-19, some words changed. In 2020 COVID-19 entered as the second most important and the relevance of the word disease increased. The topic makes semantic sense but no impact of the other viruses is apparent.

We expected better results from the DETM model. Although some results have been achieved in the ability to identify events, they are not acceptable. The deberta model

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was capable of better representing two of the three events occurring under the same topic. This is a clear indication that the model attempts to build a topic on the evolution of coronaviruses. The topic is not quite correct, but it is acceptable. The main problem is that it has not identified the MERS event.

The low model interpretability corresponds to the coherence values obtained. The coherence C_V has been low, so the semantic quality of the models is expected to be fair. But, the specificity is high, and it can be observed in the graphs. Although the model is not able to generate a good topic evolution, the words in the topic are highly related. However, this feature has not given it an advantage when measuring its ability to identify events.

The results for the word2vec model were worse. First of all, the model was unable to unite several events on the same topic. In all of them, the COVID-19 word is present. However, in the topic to which this word belongs, none of the others is present. We can draw two conclusions from this. The first is that the large volume of papers related to COVID-19 has introduced noise in the model since this word appears in a large number of topics. The second is that it is not able to find relationships between similar topics.

The model seems to be able to find relationships between words but not between concepts. That is, the model demonstrates an ability to group related words but fails to build a solid topic progression. It seems that topics do not have a defined identity and that they are just groupings of words. The results obtained correspond to the model's coherences.

7.3.2 Ability to contextualize drugs

To satisfy the second evaluation goal, it is necessary to evaluate the ability of the models to contextualize the drugs. To measure this capacity, we are going to look for the relationships that the following drugs have in their topics. The following drugs have been taken from the living guidelines for COVID-19 set by WHO⁹:

- **Corticosteroids.** This drug was strongly recommended by WHO for the treatment of severe, critical and minor patients with COVID-19 on September 2, 2020¹⁰.
- **Remdesivir.** This drug was partially recommended by the WHO for the treatment of patients with non-severe COVID-19 at increased risk of hospitalization on November 20, 2020¹¹.
- **Hydroxychloroquine.** This drug was strongly discouraged by WHO for the treatment of COVID-19 in any patient, regardless of status or severity, on December 17, 2020¹².

7.3.2.1 DTM

The DTM model has found two of the three drugs among its topics since they appeared in the WHO guidelines. The drugs found were hydroxychloroquine and corti-

⁹<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-2019-nCoV-therapeutics-2022.4>

¹⁰<https://app.magicapp.org/guideline/nBkO1E/section/nByvRL>

¹¹<https://app.magicapp.org/guideline/nBkO1E/rec/nBMO8R>

¹²<https://app.magicapp.org/guideline/nBkO1E/section/j197zj>

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costeroids. The hydroxychloroquine drug only appears in the years 2019 and 2020. The fact that the word does not appear after 2020 is a good indicator. As explained above, the WHO advised against its use after the end of 2020. However, corticosteroids appear from 1993 to the present in the topics. Both words exist in the same topic, so the model relates them to each other.

In the year 2020 hydroxychloroquine appears together with: disease, oral, efficacy, treated, corticosteroid, treatment, therapeutic, drug, dose, combination, effective, patient, therapy, option and administration.

During 1993 and 2022 corticosteroids appear next to the following words: hydroxychloroquine, clinical, treated, treatment, drug, therapeutic, combination, chronic, patient, corticosteroid, dose, interferon, therapy, oral, efficacy, administered, dos, effective, administration, disease, effect, ribavirin, prophylaxis, and option.

However, it has not been able to find the term remdesivir among the topics. Although this ability is not fully covered by DTM, it has found good contextualizations for the other drugs. The words with which they are both related and have special relevance to justify this ability are the following: treatment, therapy, patient, disease drug and dose. Thus, considering the context of these drugs and that both are present in the same topic, it is clear that the model is certainly able to relate the drugs.

The main problem is that there is no relationship with COVID-19. This implies that one cannot directly relate these drugs to COVID-19. In a corpus with more than one disease or virus, it is important that the treatment-related topics(s) are related to the disease or virus they treat. This problem causes DTM to be unable to properly contextualize the drugs.

7.3.2.2 BERTopic

The BERTopic model has found all three drugs in its topics. Moreover, all three belong to the same topic. All three are present from 2020 to the present. As we have seen in the ability to analyze events, BERTopic is not good at generating dynamic topics. Therefore, words remaining for two years on the same topic will not be taken into account as something positive.

Hydroxychloroquine, corticosteroids and remdesivir appear next to the following words: plasma, trial, treatment, overlapping, comment, covid, convalescent, microglia, pedv, clinical, patient, and meta.

From the list of words, the first things that stand out are two terms that are not very interpretable: pedv and meta. PEDV may refer to porcine epidemic diarrhea virus, but there is no way to verify this. On the other hand, meta can have many meanings, so it could be eliminated from the list. Analyzing the rest of the words, convalescent and plasma can be observed. These words may refer to convalescent plasma, a treatment that is among the WHO guidelines. On December 7, 2021, the WHO took a strong position against the use of this treatment in patients with non-severe COVID-19 and advised against its use in critically ill patients unless in the context of a clinical trial¹³.

The remaining words are: trial, treatment, overlapping, comment, covid, microglia, clinical and patient. Of these, the ones that provide the most information are treat-

¹³<https://app.magicapp.org//guideline/nBkO1E/section/nJB6MR>

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ment, trial, clinical and covid. Therefore, we can say that BERTopic can contextualize drugs because it can generate a unique topic full of treatments and relate it directly to the disease it treats.

7.3.2.3 DETM

Of the two DETM models, only the one using the deberta embeddings showed results. In the topics of the DETM deberta model, only the hydroxychloroquine drug was found. This drug only appears in one topic during the year 2021 and is related to the following words: wuhan, -ncov, hydroxychloroquine, quarantine, distancing, pre-proof, italy, april, sars-cov-, corona, containment, lockdown, journal, chest, opacity.

Unlike the other models, DETM does not find the drug in a topic surrounded by related words. Many words that appear are not even from the medical domain (such as wuhan or italy). Of the entire topic, the only words that make sense to be next to hydroxychloroquine are: sars-cov- (SARS-CoV-2) and corona.

These results are not sufficient to affirm that DETM is capable of relating the drugs. Firstly, it did not find two of the three analyzed words. Secondly, most of the words that interact with hydroxychloroquine are not from the medical context. Therefore, it is clear that DETM is not able to contextualize drugs.

7.4 Conclusions

Contrary to expectations, performance of the DETM model has been poor. From the very beginning, we observed that the learning curve for the use of this model was higher and steeper than the other models. Even so, given the results of the experiments of the authors of the model and the benefits of having a wider range of parameters, it was decided to try it out. The main benefit of having a wider range of parameters was that the more parameters, the higher the possibility of developing a solution more representative of the impact of SARS-CoV-2 in the coronavirus literature.

The BERTopic model presented a different approach and we wanted to see what impact this approach had on this work. The use of pre-trained language models is always a good indicator because it enables the introduction of context into the model. Firstly, the model does not start from scratch when trying to learn the behaviour of a topic because it knows its meaning. Secondly, the model was very easy to implement as it requires few parameters and resources. However, its method for generating dynamic topics is a great disadvantage.

The DTM model was a reliable choice. This is a model that has been part of the state of the art for a long time and has been used by a wide set of authors in different research projects. The main difficulty of this model has been its implementation. Technical restrictions made it necessary to implement it through a wrapper instead of the native Python implementation. The resources required for its implementation were very high and time consuming. Attempts were made to build other models with larger numbers of topics, but at 200 or more topics it was not possible due to timeout. This is because Magarit-3 restricts executions to 7 days.

All three models have demonstrated their abilities in the evaluation of their capabil-

ities. In fact, a large part of the results observed in the graphs correspond to the values obtained through the coherence metrics. In this section, all these values have been summarized through the table 7.5. This table shows the coherences of each model for each year and the time taken to train each one.

Model	Year	C_v	UCI	NPMI	UMass	Training time
DTM	2022	0.692	2.556	0.229	3.889	43h 7m
	2021	0.725	2.724	0.252	3.743	
	2020	0.725	2.801	0.255	3.739	
	2019	0.710	2.803	0.246	3.834	
	2018	0.724	2.803	0.260	3.592	
BERTopic	2022	0.716	1.560	0.176	2.336	5h 21m
	2021	0.714	1.557	0.175	2.366	
	2020	0.710	1.523	0.173	2.360	
	2019	0.469	-1.475	0.012	5.042	
	2018	0.439	-1.689	-0.006	5.163	
DETM deberta	2022	0.460	-1.594	-0.037	5.241	7h 40m
	2021	0.439	-1.368	-0.029	5.274	
	2020	0.443	-1.780	-0.043	5.392	
	2019	0.444	-1.708	-0.037	5.797	
	2018	0.450	-1.386	-0.026	5.113	
DETM word2vec	2022	0.412	-0.060	-0.004	1.671	12h 14m
	2021	0.414	-0.058	-0.004	1.674	
	2020	0.418	-0.042	-0.001	1.690	
	2019	0.423	-0.027	0.001	1.733	
	2018	0.432	0.002	0.005	1.802	

Table 7.5: All model coherences for different dates.

According to the DTM model, the main conclusion of this work is that the coronavirus topic tends to decrease. Trends only appear when the virus has spread to humans. As can be seen in the three events during this century, there have been three times that a virus of the coronavirus family has spread to humans. Each time this has occurred, research interest and publications have increased.

In addition, the growth in relevance appears to match the relevance of the contagious. SARS-CoV-1 was declared an epidemic and has reached higher relevance than MERS-CoV. Similarly, SARS-CoV-2, which has caused the COVID-19 pandemic, grows in relevance almost vertically. In a few years, if this model is fed with new papers SARS-CoV-2 may increase much more in size. After all, this time it has been a pandemic, not an epidemic.

Because of the number of years covered in the corpus and the number of topics, it is very difficult to cover all. It is quite possible that there are more events that have affected the coronavirus literature. It is even likely that there are topics within coronaviruses that have a representation in the DTM model (since it has proven to be more powerful than the others for this task), and this has been affected by different elements and events. In other words, the DTM model is still a world to be discovered since only one of the topics present has been visualized.

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Dynamic topic models have proven to be an effective tool in analyzing how the coronavirus issue has evolved over the years. Especially the DTM model. These tools provide the ability to analyze a large collection of documents and extract the information of interest.

All the material developed, results and conclusions are being described in a scientific paper for publication. However, the trained models, preprocessed dataset, context-stopwords and other resources are available in the zenodo resource of Guillen Pacho.

Future work would be to try to get a better performance from the DETM model. The use of perplexity as an error metric does not seem to give good results for coherence. This work should evolve towards creating an error function that evaluates coherence and corrects it epoch after epoch.

Bibliography

- G. Salton, A. Wong, and C. S. Yang. A vector space model for automatic indexing. *Commun. ACM*, 18(11):613–620, nov 1975. ISSN 0001-0782. doi: 10.1145/361219.361220.
- ELEANOR Ide and Gerard Salton. Interactive search strategies and dynamic file organization in information retrieval. *The Smart system-experiments in automatic document processing*, pages 373–393, 1971.
- Peter D Turney and Patrick Pantel. From frequency to meaning: Vector space models of semantics. *Journal of artificial intelligence research*, 37:141–188, 2010.
- Zellig S Harris. Distributional structure. *Word*, 10(2-3):146–162, 1954.
- Scott Deerwester, Susan T Dumais, George W Furnas, Thomas K Landauer, and Richard Harshman. Indexing by latent semantic analysis. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 41(6):391–407, 1990. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1097-4571\(199009\)41:6<391::AID-ASI1>3.0.CO;2-9](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1097-4571(199009)41:6<391::AID-ASI1>3.0.CO;2-9).
- Zi Yin and Yuanyuan Shen. On the dimensionality of word embedding. In S. Bengio, H. Wallach, H. Larochelle, K. Grauman, N. Cesa-Bianchi, and R. Garnett, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 31. Curran Associates, Inc., 2018.
- Luis Gutiérrez and Brian Keith. A systematic literature review on word embeddings. In Jezreel Mejia, Mirna Muñoz, Álvaro Rocha, Adriana Peña, and Marco Pérez-Cisneros, editors, *Trends and Applications in Software Engineering*, pages 132–141, Cham, 2019. Springer International Publishing. ISBN 978-3-030-01171-0.
- Tomas Mikolov, Kai Chen, Greg Corrado, and Jeffrey Dean. Efficient estimation of word representations in vector space. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1301.3781*, 2013a.
- Tomás Mikolov, Ilya Sutskever, Kai Chen, Greg Corrado, and Jeffrey Dean. Distributed representations of words and phrases and their compositionality. *CoRR*, abs/1310.4546, 2013b.
- Jeffrey Pennington, Richard Socher, and Christopher Manning. GloVe: Global vectors for word representation. In *Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, pages 1532–1543, Doha, Qatar, October 2014. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.3115/v1/D14-1162.
- Tomás Mikolov, Edouard Grave, Piotr Bojanowski, Christian Puhersch, and Armand Joulin. Advances in pre-training distributed word representations. *CoRR*, abs/1712.09405, 2017.

- Kilian Q. Weinberger, Anirban Dasgupta, Josh Attenberg, John Langford, and Alexander J. Smola. Feature hashing for large scale multitask learning. *CoRR*, abs/0902.2206, 2009.
- Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee, and Kristina Toutanova. BERT: pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. *CoRR*, abs/1810.04805, 2018.
- Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention is all you need. *CoRR*, abs/1706.03762, 2017.
- Yinhan Liu, Myle Ott, Naman Goyal, Jingfei Du, Mandar Joshi, Danqi Chen, Omer Levy, Mike Lewis, Luke Zettlemoyer, and Veselin Stoyanov. Roberta: A robustly optimized bert pretraining approach, 2019.
- Pengcheng He, Xiaodong Liu, Jianfeng Gao, and Weizhu Chen. Deberta: Decoding-enhanced bert with disentangled attention, 2020.
- Nils Reimers and Iryna Gurevych. Sentence-bert: Sentence embeddings using siamese bert-networks, 2019.
- Hans Peter Luhn. The automatic creation of literature abstracts. *IBM Journal of research and development*, 2(2):159–165, 1958.
- Akiko Aizawa. An information-theoretic perspective of tf-idf measures. *Information Processing Management*, 39(1):45–65, 2003. ISSN 0306-4573. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0306-4573\(02\)00021-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0306-4573(02)00021-3).
- Karen Spärck Jones. A statistical interpretation of term specificity and its application in retrieval. *Journal of documentation*, 1972.
- Thomas Hofmann. Probabilistic latent semantic indexing. In *Proceedings of the 22nd annual international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval*, pages 50–57, 1999.
- David Blei, Andrew Ng, and Michael Jordan. Latent dirichlet allocation. In T. Dietterich, S. Becker, and Z. Ghahramani, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 14. MIT Press, 2001.
- David M Blei, Andrew Y Ng, and Michael I Jordan. Latent dirichlet allocation. *Journal of machine Learning research*, 3(Jan):993–1022, 2003.
- Matthew Hoffman, Francis Bach, and David Blei. Online learning for latent dirichlet allocation. *advances in neural information processing systems*, 23, 2010.
- David Blei and John Lafferty. Correlated topic models. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 18:147, 2006a.
- Yee Whye Teh, Michael I Jordan, Matthew J Beal, and David M Blei. Hierarchical dirichlet processes. *Journal of the american statistical association*, 101(476):1566–1581, 2006.
- Adji B. Dieng, Francisco J. R. Ruiz, and David M. Blei. Topic modeling in embedding spaces, 2019a.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Dimo Angelov. Top2vec: Distributed representations of topics. *CoRR*, abs/2008.09470, 2020.
- Maarten Grootendorst. Bertopic: Neural topic modeling with a class-based tf-idf procedure, 2022.
- Thomas Hofmann, Jan Puzicha, and Michael Jordan. Learning from dyadic data. In M. Kearns, S. Solla, and D. Cohn, editors, *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, volume 11. MIT Press, 1998.
- Andrea Lancichinetti, M. Irmak Sirer, Jane X. Wang, Daniel Acuna, Konrad Kording, and Luis A. Nunes Amaral. High-reproducibility and high-accuracy method for automated topic classification. *Phys. Rev. X*, 5:011007, Jan 2015. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevX.5.011007.
- Ridwan Marqas, Saman Almufti, and Rasheed Rebar. Comparing Symmetric and Asymmetric cryptography in message encryption and decryption by using AES and RSA algorithms. *Xi'an Jianzhu Keji Daxue Xuebao/Journal of Xi'an University of Architecture & Technology*, 12:3110–3116, March 2020. doi: 10.37896/JXAT12.03/262.
- David M Blei and John D Lafferty. Dynamic topic models. In *Proceedings of the 23rd international conference on Machine learning*, pages 113–120, 2006b.
- Xuerui Wang and Andrew McCallum. Topics over time: A non-markov continuous-time model of topical trends. In *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*, KDD '06, page 424–433, New York, NY, USA, 2006. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 1595933395. doi: 10.1145/1150402.1150450.
- Lu Ren, David B. Dunson, and Lawrence Carin. The dynamic hierarchical dirichlet process. In *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Machine Learning*, ICML '08, page 824–831, New York, NY, USA, 2008. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781605582054. doi: 10.1145/1390156.1390260.
- Chong Wang, David Blei, and David Heckerman. Continuous time dynamic topic models, 2012.
- Adji B. Dieng, Francisco J. R. Ruiz, and David M. Blei. The dynamic embedded topic model, 2019b.
- Hanna M Wallach, Iain Murray, Ruslan Salakhutdinov, and David Mimno. Evaluation methods for topic models. In *Proceedings of the 26th annual international conference on machine learning*, pages 1105–1112, 2009.
- David Newman, Jey Han Lau, Karl Grieser, and Timothy Baldwin. Automatic evaluation of topic coherence. In *Human language technologies: The 2010 annual conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics*, pages 100–108, 2010.
- Nikolaos Aletras and Mark Stevenson. Evaluating topic coherence using distributional semantics. In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Computational Semantics (IWCS 2013) – Long Papers*, pages 13–22, Potsdam, Germany, March 2013. Association for Computational Linguistics.

- Michael Röder, Andreas Both, and Alexander Hinneburg. Exploring the space of topic coherence measures. In *Proceedings of the Eighth ACM International Conference on Web Search and Data Mining*, WSDM '15, page 399–408, New York, NY, USA, 2015. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9781450333177. doi: 10.1145/2684822.2685324.
- David Mimno, Hanna Wallach, Edmund Talley, Miriam Leenders, and Andrew McCallum. Optimizing semantic coherence in topic models. In *Proceedings of the 2011 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, pages 262–272, Edinburgh, Scotland, UK., July 2011. Association for Computational Linguistics.
- Lucy Lu Wang, Kyle Lo, Yoganand Chandrasekhar, Russell Reas, Jiangjiang Yang, Darrin Eide, Kathryn Funk, Rodney Michael Kinney, Ziyang Liu, William Cooper Merrill, Paul Mooney, Dewey A. Murdick, Devvret Rishi, Jerry Sheehan, Zhihong Shen, Brandon Stilson, Alex D Wade, Kuansan Wang, Christopher Wilhelm, Boya Xie, Douglas A. Raymond, Daniel S. Weld, Oren Etzioni, and Sebastian Kohlmeier. Cord-19: The covid-19 open research dataset. *ArXiv*, 2020.
- Daniel Maier, A. Waldherr, P. Miltner, G. Wiedemann, A. Niekler, A. Keinert, B. Pfetsch, G. Heyer, U. Reber, T. Häussler, H. Schmid-Petri, and S. Adam. Applying lda topic modeling in communication research: Toward a valid and reliable methodology. *Communication Methods and Measures*, 12(2-3):93–118, 2018. doi: 10.1080/19312458.2018.1430754.
- Michael Röder, Andreas Both, and Alexander Hinneburg. Exploring the space of topic coherence measures. In *Proceedings of the eighth ACM international conference on Web search and data mining*, pages 399–408, 2015.
- Ibai Guillen Pacho. Resources of impact of sars-cov-2 on the coronavirus literature through dynamic topics.

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